

Studies on the Kinetics of Hydrolytic Equilibria of Oxo-bromomolybdates(V) and their Comparative Studies with the corresponding Oxo-chloro Species

K. RAY^b, T. K. ROYCHAUDHURY^a, H. K. SAHA^a and D. C. MUKHERJEE^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Scottish Church College, Calcutta-700 006

Manuscript received 13 January 1995, revised 5 May 1995, accepted 25 July 1995

Kinetics of the hydrolysis of MoOCl_2^{2-} , MoOBr_2^{2-} and MoOBr_4^- have been studied. Three different kinetic steps have been identified. Probable mechanisms for all the processes have been suggested on the basis of the observed kinetic parameters. The proposed scheme for the process,

predicts the involvement of some transient intermediate species. The identical behaviour of MoOBr_2^{2-} and MoOBr_4^- ions in aqueous solution has been observed. Activation parameters for chloro- and bromo-systems have been determined. A positive ΔS^\ddagger values for MoOCl_2^{2-} and a negative value for the same for MoOBr_2^{2-} and MoOBr_4^- are observed, indicating a dissociative mechanism for the chloro-system and an associative mechanism for the bromo-system for the process, $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3^{4+} \rightarrow \text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4^{2+}$. The difference in the chloro- and bromo-systems has been explained. Dependence of halide ion and hydrogen ion concentration in the hydrolytic behaviour of oxohalomolybdates(V) has also been explained.

Molybdenum(V) exists as monomeric species MoOCl_2^{2-} in 6 M HCl acid¹ and in more dilute acid it exists as dimers as revealed from electronic^{1,2} and epr³ spectra and other studies^{4,5}. Some workers⁶ predicted the presence of at least two dimeric forms and the thermodynamic and spectral study of the sequence

indicated the involvement of two H^+ ions in the monomer-dimer conversion process, supporting earlier observation of Haight². From symmetry considerations, the existence of diamagnetic *cis* and *trans* mono-oxobridged (C_{2v} and D_{2h} symmetry) and paramagnetic skew form of the isomer (D_{2d} symmetry) and also at a still lower acid concentration, the existence of a diamagnetic di- μ -oxodimer were established⁶. Such inter conversions in some bromo compounds have also been reported^{8,9}.

But in spite of the above mentioned studies, the nature and mechanism of the dimerisation process and particularly of the hydrolytic process is not yet known. The magnetic susceptibility⁴, epr³ and spectrophotometric² studies were carried out at different metal ion $[\text{Mo}^V]$ concentrations and could not be meaningfully compared. Thus, while some spectral data are available, the structural details of the species present and their relative quantities as function of $[\text{Mo}^V]$, $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and temperature are not yet clear. The literature survey indicates that although some oxidation and ligand exchange kinetics of $[\text{Mo}^V]$ have been reported¹⁰, very little information regarding the hydrolytic process involving Mo^V is available.

The lower stability of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Br}_8^{4-}$ in water than the

corresponding chloro compound, the overlap of its λ_{max} with the *d-d* transition peak and the precipitation the intermediate hydroxo species¹¹ probably render the spectral and kinetic studies with the bromo compound difficult. We, through judicious selection of the proper solvent, have been able to remove some of the difficulties so as to perform some appropriate experiments. The present communication deals with detailed kinetic studies of the hydrolytic reactions of MoOCl_2^{2-} , MoOBr_2^{2-} and MoOBr_4^- species by stopped-flow spectrophotometer, as the processes are fairly fast at room temperature.

The pH used in studies of interconversions involving different oxidation states of Mo to provide biological model systems, was such that the hydrolytic process was the primary one. So, for a better understanding of the biological processes, the kinetics and mechanism of the hydrolytic process should be established. Furthermore, monomeric Mo^V is the actual reductant for the reduction of nitrate between pH 2.2 and 3.5¹². As the monomeric Mo^V undergoes hydrolysis forming dimeric Mo^V at the said pH range, the kinetics of the hydrolytic process is an important part of the whole redox process and need attention. In the present communication, the kinetic parameters for the entire process have been evaluated and temperature, H^+ and Br^- ion dependence have been studied.

Results and Discussion

Time-absorbance data for the hydrolysis of MoOCl_2^{2-} , MoOBr_2^{2-} and that of MoOBr_4^- solution in acetonitrile at different acid concentrations but constant halide ion concentrations and at different halide ion concentrations at constant acid concentration predict the existence of three

(B) (B')

(B') (C)

(B) (B'')

(B'') (C)

In this case also the uncatalysed process proceeds through heptacoordination and octacoordination for the catalysed process. The formation of aqua-complex might also take

Fig. 1. Effect of $[\text{H}^+](M)$ on observed rate constants (s^{-1}) for the process II.

place in this case as a primary process but it could not be followed since the process is faster in comparison to the hydrolysis. The intermediate transient ion species being short-lived, as is evident from the reaction time, one can provide an indirect reasoning in support of the above speculative mechanism. The increase in the molar conductance values of MoOCl_2^{2-} with dilution¹ and its approach to a limiting value at infinite dilution suggest an increasing dissociation with dilution and thus provide support for a dissociative mechanism, forming ions, as formulated in our scheme. Also, the earlier isolation of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2^{6+}$ moiety¹⁷ provides further support with the assumption that

$$[k_2|A'| + k_3|A''|] \gg [k_5|B'| + k_7|B''| - k_5 + k_7|B|]$$

and following the sequence one can deduce equations in the following form.

Step II :

$$(k_{\text{obs}})_2 = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1}} \frac{1}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{k_3 k_4}{k_{-3}} [\text{Br}^-]^2$$

Step III :

$$(k_{\text{obs}})_3 = \frac{k_5 k_6}{k_{-5}} \frac{1}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{k_7 k_8}{k_{-7}} [\text{Br}^-]^2$$

Fig. 2. Effect of $[\text{H}^+](M)$ on observed rate constants (s^{-1}) for the process II.

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS WITH TEMPERATURE*

Compd.	Temp. °C	$(k_{\text{obs}})_1$	$(k_{\text{obs}})_2$	$(k_{\text{obs}})_3$	ΔH^\ddagger (kcal mol ⁻¹)			ΔS^\ddagger (e.u.)		
					I	II	III	I	II	III
					[Metal ion] = $2 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{H}^+] 0.5 M$, $\mu = 0.5 M$					
$(\text{PyH})_2(\text{MoOCl}_5)$	20	214	3.5	0.4						
	30	232	7.1	1.7	2.7	12.4	22.6	-38.6	-13.8	16
	35	290	9.0	2.7						
	40	317	12.5	5.3						
$(\text{PyH})_2(\text{MoOBr}_5)$	20	423	25.0	2.7						
	30	446	47.0	6.4	0.3	11.1	13.7	-45.3	-14.2	-9
	35	457	67.0	8.9						
	40	469	90.0	13.2						
$(\text{PyH})(\text{MoOBr}_4)$	20		25.0	2.7						
	30		41.0	5.7		10.7	13.3		-15.5	-11
	35		66.0	8.7						
	40		84.0	12.0						

*Experimental error = 5–6%.

Both the equations suggest that the observed rate constant should vary linearly with $1/[H^+]^2$ at constant Br^- ion concentration with a positive slope and intercept (Figs. 1 and 2). The experimental observation supports the prediction. The equations also suggest that the observed rate constants should vary linearly with the square of Br^- ion concentration at constant H^+ ion concentration with a positive slope and intercept. This prediction is found to corroborate the experimental observation at lower Br^- ion concentration.

Fig. 3. Effect of $[Br^-]$ (M) on observed rate constants (s^{-1}) for the process II.

After a certain value of Br^- ion concentration the observed rate constant is found to decrease (Table 2, Figs. 3 and 4). This is probably due to the fact that since Br^- ion is a product of the parallel reaction, the catalyst at higher concentration acts as a reactant and inhibits the reaction. The mechanism of Br^- ion inhibition at higher concentration is beyond the scope of this study and requires separate attention. The effect of Br^- ion concentration should be more pronounced as predicted by the schemes and is supported by the experimental observations. The Br^- ion concentration at which the observed rate constants begins to decrease is more or less the same in both the steps, suggesting identity of the two processes in the two steps. We did not venture to evaluate the individual rate constants. However,

Fig. 4. Effect of $[Br^-]$ (M) on observed rate constants (s^{-1}) for the process III.

this will not serve any meaningful purpose for the present study and will constitute a separate study.

Temperature dependence of the processes : The reactions were followed at four different temperatures between 20 and 40°. The estimated kinetic parameters are given in Table 3. It is found that ΔH^\ddagger quantities for $MoOCl_2^{2-}$ and $MoOBr_2^{2-}$ and $MoOBr_4^-$ are comparable. For the fastest process which was logically assumed to be a diffusion-controlled process, is supported by the frequency factor and E^* values. The activation entropy quantities ΔS^\ddagger , suggest a different situation for the step III of chloro and bromo systems. The more negative values of ΔS^\ddagger for the bromo system suggest a larger extent of solvation in the transition state and thus decreasing the internal degrees of freedom than that of the transition state of the chloro system. The effect is more pronounced in nonaqueous solvents¹⁸.

The d^1 -complexes of Mo^V have higher positive charge on the central atom and it would be predicted on electrostatic grounds alone that they would react more rapidly by a displacement mechanism¹⁹. A reasonable assumption might be that all such complexes are reacting by an S_N2 mechanism in which a seventh group must be added to the coordination sphere in keeping with the valence bond theory, such a process is greatly facilitated if any empty d -orbital is available to the incoming group²⁰. If such an orbital is not available, then the seventh group must add by using outer d -orbital of lower stability. This reaction becomes slower because a higher activation energy is required (Table 3). The probable mechanism of the overall process is presented in Scheme 1.

The inherent difference in the hydrolytic intermediates for chloro and bromo systems lies in the fact that size and electronegativity of chloride and bromide ligands are different. Bonding consideration for the linear $Mo_2O_3^{4+}$ bridge has been discussed elsewhere²¹. The available structural evidence seems to implicate the diamagnetic *cis* or *trans* forms of $Mo_2O_3^{4+}$ dimers are lower in energy than the paramagnetic skew form. However, the possibility of a small barrier to rotation associated with a small singlet-triplet energy difference can not be eliminated. Thus in solution an equilibrium between paramagnetic and diamagnetic forms may be present or the paramagnetic form may occur as an intermediate in the interconversion of *cis* and *trans* structures²². The activation energy and enthalpy data in step III of the chloro system ensures a greater stability of the $Mo_2O_3^{4+}$ moiety for the chloro complex than that of the bromo system (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. *Cis*, *skew* and *trans* isomers of monooxobridged Mo^V .

Scheme 1

Experimental

HBr (A.R.) was double-distilled over red phosphorus and the distillate was tested to be free from bromine. Acids of different strengths were prepared through titrations against a standard alkali. Acetonitrile (A.R.) was double-distilled over P_2O_5 and preserved in sealed coloured bottles. Effect of non-aqueous solvent on the pHs of dilute HCl and HBr (prepared specifically by theoretical calculations) was followed by a Systronics 335 pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit) at experimental temperatures. Electronic spectra of the compounds in different concentrations of HBr, HCl acid and in acetonitrile were recorded in a Varian 634 spectrophotometer. All the solutions were deoxygenated by passing nitrogen gas just before experiments. Absorption maxima at 500 nm for chloro(Mo_2O_3)⁴⁺ and 530 nm for bromo(Mo_2O_3)⁴⁺ compounds were monitored for stopped-

flow experiments^{4,23}. By monitoring the spectra and by several trials and scanning of the time scale, it was possible to identify three different steps corresponding to three time spans, namely, (i) 1–5, (ii) 5–10 and (iii) 10–100 ms. Complexes $(PyH)_2(MoOCl_5)$, $(PyH)_2(MoOBr_5)$ and $(PyH)(MoOBr_4)$ were prepared by standard methods²⁴. (PyH) -salts were chosen for their purity and also in the chosen acid range (Py) has greater affinity for H^+ ions, forming $(PyH)^+$ ions, having no liganding property. The kinetics of the reactions were followed and the observed rate constants were determined with the help of a stopped-flow spectrophotometer (Photal RA 401) fitted with a computer and thermostat (Hakka F-3; $\pm 0.02^\circ$).

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the helpful discus-

sions with Dr. P. Banerjee of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, and Dr. S. S. Mondal, Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University. They thank the authority of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science for facilities for using the stopped-flow spectrophotometer, and also thankful to Miss Madhuchhanda Mitra, Department of Applied Physics, Calcutta University, for partial assistance in processing the data.

References

1. R. G. JAMES and WARDLAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2145.
2. G. P. HAIGHT, JR., *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 303.
3. C. R. HARE, I. BERNAL and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 831.
4. W. BACK, W. DANZER and G. THIBLE, *Angew Chem. Intl. Ed. Engl.*, 1973, 12, 582.
5. L. SACCONI and R. CINI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4239.
6. R. COLTON and G. R. SCOLLARY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, 21, 1427; R. COLTON and G. ROSE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, 21, 883.
7. M. ARDON and A. PERNICK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, 12, 2484.
8. H. K. SAHA and A. K. BANERJEE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 697, 1861; R. D. DOWSING and J. F. GIBSON, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 655; H. KON and N. E. SHARPLESS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 105.
9. J. F. ALLEN and H. M. NEWMANN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1612.
10. J. T. SPENCE and H. Y. Y. CHANG, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 319; T. M. TAM and J. H. SWINEHART, "Pacific Conference on Chemistry and Spectroscopy", San Francisco, 1974, Abstr. No 101; D. D. DEVORE and E. A. MAALTA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, 24, 2846; K. C. SU and K. C. WOO, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 7, 158; C. Y. CHOU, D. D. DEVORE, S. C. KUCKETT, E. A. MAALTA, J. C. HUFFMAN and F. TAKUSAGAWA, *Polyhedron*, 1986, 5, 301; R. A. EL-ZARU and H. A. HODALI, *Polyhedron*, 1990, 9, 113; M. C. GHOSH and E. S. GOULD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, 29, 4258.
11. R. A. D. WENTWORTH and T. S. PIPER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, 41, 3885; C. D. GARNER, I. H. HILLIER, J. KENDRICK and F. E. MABBS, *Nature*, 1975, 258, 134.
12. E. P. GUYMON and J. T. SPENCE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 1964.
13. A. Y. FRIDMAN, S. D. ERSHOVA and N. M. DYATLOVA, *Koord. Khim.*, 1978, 7, 1849 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 90, 77253); S. L. JAIN and R. C. KAPOOR, *Proc. Natl. Sci. Acad. India, Sect. A*, 1980, 46, 53.
14. K. L. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics", 2nd. ed., Tata McGraw-Hill, New Delhi, 1986, p.205.
15. R. D. TAYLOR and J. T. SPENCE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 14, 2815.
16. B. R. MCGARVEY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 476.
17. H. K. SAHA, R. K. PRAMANIK and B. K. SIKDAR, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1976, 53, 30; H. K. SAHA and T. K. ROYCHOWDHARY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 698.
18. F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, "Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1973, p.129.
19. C. D. GARNER, M. R. HYDE, F. E. MABBS and V. I. ROUTLEDGE, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 1175.
20. Ref. 18, p.144.
21. A. B. BHAKKE, F. A. COLTON and J. S. WOOD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3024; B. BLUES, D. H. BROWN, R. G. PERKINS and J. J. P. STEWART, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1974, 8, 67.
22. *Prog Inorg. Chem.*, 22, 74.
23. E. B. FLEISCHER and T. S. SRIVASTAVA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1972, 5, 151.
24. E. A. ALLEN, B. I. BRISDEN, D. A. EDWARDS, G. W. A. FOWLES and R. G. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4649; P. M. BOORMAN, C. D. GARNER and F. E. MABBS, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 1299.